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Distribution Network Data

Table 1 – Bus Data

Node	P _a (W)	Q _a (VAr)	P _b	Q _b	P _c	Q _c	Node	P _a (W)	Q _a (VAr)	P _b	Q _b	P _c	Q _c
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	69	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	70	2147	914	2147	914	2147	914
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	71	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
4	13800	5879	13800	5879	13800	5879	72	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	73	2607	1110	2607	1110	2607	1110
6	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	74	583	248	583	248	583	248
7	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	75	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
8	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	76	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
9	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	77	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
10	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	78	1809	771	1809	771	1809	771
11	0	0	0	0	0	0	79	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	0	0	0	0	80	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
13	2637	1123	2637	1123	2637	1123	81	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
14	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	82	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
15	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	83	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	84	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
17	13800	5879	13800	5879	13800	5879	85	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
18	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	86	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	87	4753	2025	4753	2025	4753	2025
20	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	88	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
21	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	89	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
22	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	90	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
23	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	91	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	0	0	0	0	0	0	92	13800	5879	13800	5879	13800	5879
25	920	392	920	392	920	392	93	0	0	0	0	0	0
26	13800	5879	13800	5879	13800	5879	94	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
27	0	0	0	0	0	0	95	7207	3070	7207	3070	7207	3070
28	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	96	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	0	0	0	0	0	0	97	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
30	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	98	1840	784	1840	784	1840	784
31	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	99	0	0	0	0	0	0
32	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	100	7207	3070	7207	3070	7207	3070
33	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	101	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
34	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	102	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
35	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	103	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
36	0	0	0	0	0	0	104	0	0	0	0	0	0
37	3803	1620	3803	1620	3803	1620	105	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
38	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	106	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
39	0	0	0	0	0	0	107	33273	14174	33273	14174	33273	14174
40	920	392	920	392	920	392	108	0	0	0	0	0	0
41	0	0	0	0	0	0	109	0	0	0	0	0	0
42	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	110	33273	14174	33273	14174	33273	14174
43	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	111	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
44	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	112	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
45	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	113	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798
46	13800	5879	13800	5879	13800	5879	114	0	0	0	0	0	0
47	307	131	307	131	307	131	115	0	0	0	0	0	0
48	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	116	9200	3919	9200	3919	9200	3919
49	0	0	0	0	0	0	117	9200	3919	9200	3919	9200	3919
50	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	118	9200	3919	9200	3919	9200	3919
51	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	119	9200	3919	9200	3919	9200	3919
52	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	120	0	0	0	0	0	0
53	0	0	0	0	0	0	121	9200	3919	9200	3919	9200	3919
54	368	157	368	157	368	157	122	16867	7185	16867	7185	16867	7185
55	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	123	0	0	0	0	0	0
56	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	124	0	0	0	0	0	0
57	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	125	4753	2025	4753	2025	4753	2025
58	0	0	0	0	0	0	126	4753	2025	4753	2025	4753	2025
59	3067	1306	3067	1306	3067	1306	127	13800	5879	13800	5879	13800	5879
60	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697	128	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
61	1165	496	1165	496	1165	496	129	0	0	0	0	0	0
62	920	392	920	392	920	392	130	13800	5879	13800	5879	13800	5879
63	1687	719	1687	719	1687	719	131	0	0	0	0	0	0
64	0	0	0	0	0	0	132	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
65	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	133	0	0	0	0	0	0
66	23000	9798	23000	9798	23000	9798	134	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
67	1073	457	1073	457	1073	457	135	34500	14697	34500	14697	34500	14697
68	0	0	0	0	0	0	136	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2 – Line Data

From node	To node	Branch length (km)	Cable Type	Rate of Permanent Faults (faults/km/year)	Rate of Temporary Faults	Percentage of Residential Consumers *	Percentage of Commercial Consumers *	Percentage of Industrial Consumers *	Number of Consumers Per Phase *
136	1	-	Transf	-	-	50	30	20	0
1	2	0.9	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
2	3	0.05	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
3	4	0.1	3	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
3	5	0.04	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
5	6	0.2	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
6	7	0.2	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
7	8	0.2	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
8	9	0.01	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
9	10	0.05	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
10	11	0.1	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
11	12	0.06	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	0
12	13	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
13	14	0.16	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
14	15	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
12	16	0.01	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
16	17	0.02	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
17	18	0.04	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
18	19	0.04	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	0
19	20	0.05	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
20	21	0.15	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
19	22	0.03	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
11	23	0.07	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
23	24	0.05	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
24	25	0.02	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
25	26	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
26	27	0.06	2	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	0
27	28	0.04	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
28	29	0.02	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	0
29	30	0.12	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
30	31	0.02	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
29	32	0.02	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
27	33	0.005	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
33	34	0.025	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
34	35	0.01	3	0.072	0.98	70	25	5	30
24	36	0.07	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
36	37	0.01	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
37	38	0.01	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
38	39	0.07	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
39	40	0.1	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
39	41	0.06	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
41	42	0.05	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
41	43	0.01	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
43	44	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
41	45	0.04	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
45	46	0.06	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
39	47	0.02	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
47	48	0.12	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
48	49	0.05	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
49	50	0.02	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
50	51	0.17	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
51	52	0.1	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
49	53	0.06	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	0
53	54	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
54	55	0.13	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
55	56	0.02	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
53	57	0.08	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
57	58	0.05	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	0
58	59	0.06	3	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
58	60	0.02	3	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
60	61	0.04	3	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
49	62	0.01	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
62	63	0.05	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
63	64	0.03	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
64	65	0.02	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
65	66	0.03	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
66	67	0.02	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
67	68	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	0
68	69	0.02	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
68	70	0.02	2	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
70	71	0.05	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
68	72	0.04	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
72	73	0.04	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
73	74	0.02	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20

74	75	0.11	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
75	76	0.02	4	0.072	0.98	15	5	80	20
64	77	0.03	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
77	78	0.05	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
78	79	0.07	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
79	80	0.07	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
80	81	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
81	82	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
82	83	0.05	2	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	0
83	84	0.05	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
83	85	0.03	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
85	86	0.03	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
86	129	0.02	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
129	87	0.13	3	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
87	88	0.005	1	0.072	0.98	50	30	20	10
79	89	0.05	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
79	90	0.18	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
90	91	0.02	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
91	92	0.03	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
92	93	0.07	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
93	94	0.1	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
93	95	0.04	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
93	96	0.05	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
96	97	0.06	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
96	98	0.11	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
98	99	0.04	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
99	100	0.11	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
99	101	0.06	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
101	102	0.04	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
96	103	0.03	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
103	104	0.15	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
104	105	0.21	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
104	106	0.03	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
106	107	0.1	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
107	108	0.1	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
108	109	0.03	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
109	110	0.02	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
110	111	0.17	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
111	112	0.11	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
108	113	0.11	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
113	114	0.2	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
114	115	0.2	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
114	116	0.2	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
116	117	0.2	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
117	118	0.11	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
118	119	0.07	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
91	120	0.07	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
120	121	0.07	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
121	122	0.13	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
120	123	0.02	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
123	124	0.02	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
124	125	0.04	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
124	126	0.04	2	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
126	127	0.02	1	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
127	128	0.06	3	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
129	130	0.07	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
105	131	0.02	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
131	132	0.1	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
131	133	0.04	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	0
133	134	0.04	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5
134	135	0.04	4	0.072	0.98	5	10	85	5

* Loads are connected to the end node.

$$Z_{cable1} = [0.4272 + j0.9609 \ 0.06 + j0.478 \ 0.06 + j0.450 \ 0.06 + j0.478 \ 0.4272 + j0.9609 \ 0.06 + j0.536 \ 0.06 + j0.450 \ 0.06 + j0.536 \ 0.4272 + j0.9609] \Omega/km$$

$$Z_{cable2} = [1.644 + j1.006 \ 0.06 + j0.478 \ 0.06 + j0.450 \ 0.06 + j0.478 \ 1.644 + j1.006 \ 0.06 + j0.536 \ 0.06 + j0.450 \ 0.06 + j0.536 \ 1.644 + j1.006] \Omega/km$$

$$Z_{cable3} = [1.084 + j0.998 \ 0.06 + j0.478 \ 0.06 + j0.450 \ 0.06 + j0.478 \ 1.084 + j0.998 \ 0.06 + j0.536 \ 0.06 + j0.450 \ 0.06 + j0.536 \ 1.084 + j0.998] \Omega/km$$

$$Z_{cable4} = [0.7567 + j1.0067 \ 0.06 + j0.478 \ 0.06 + j0.450 \ 0.06 + j0.478 \ 0.7567 + j1.0067 \ 0.06 + j0.536 \ 0.06 + j0.450 \ 0.06 + j0.536 \ 0.7567 + j1.0067] \Omega/km$$

$$Z_{Transf} = [0.3790 + j3.7890 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0.3790 + j3.7890 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0.3790 + j3.7890] \Omega$$

Cable 1 (4/0) Current Limit = 340 A Cable 2 (#4) Current Limit = 140 A Cable 3 (#2) Current Limit = 180 A Cable 4 (1/0) Current Limit = 230 A

Table 3 – Distributed Generators Data

Generator	Capacity (kVA)	Cut in Wind (m/s)	Cut off Wind (m/s)	Nominal Wind (m/s)	Transient Impedance (Ω)
DG 1	1000	-	-	-	0.0692 + j19.8322
DG 2	1000	-	-	-	0.0692 + j19.8322
DG 3	1000	-	-	-	0.0692 + j19.8322
Wind Farm	1000	4	25	13	0.0692 + j19.8322
Solar Farm	50	-	-	-	-

Each generator is connected to the distribution system through a 13.8/6.6 kV transformer with $X = 0.06$ pu and $R = 0.007$ pu and corresponding apparent power.

Table 4 – Stochastic Variables Parameters

Variable	Probability Density Function	PDF Parameters
Load	Normal	$\mu =$ node nominal power, $\sigma = 0.4*\mu/3$
Wind Speed	Weibull	$\alpha = 2.22, \beta = 9.70$
Solar Irradiation	Uniform (Real)	Min = 0.0, Max = 1.0
Fault Location	Uniform (Integer)	Min = 1, Max = 136
Fault Impedance	Lognormal	$\mu = 1.60944 [\ln(5)], \sigma = 1$

The fault type is modelled as follows: 60% single phase, 20% phase-phase, 15% three-phase, 5% two-phase-ground. Faults are applied in all phases for every fault type, *e.g.*, a single phase fault may be applied to phase A, B or C, according to a uniform distribution.

The wind farm power ($S_{windfarm}$) in each iteration is calculated as follows:

$$S_{windfarm} = \begin{cases} S_{nom}, & \text{if } 13 \leq wind_{speed} < 25 \\ 0, & \text{if } wind_{speed} \geq 25 \\ S_{nom} * \left(\frac{wind_{speed}^2 - cut_{in}^2}{wind_{nominal}^2 - cut_{in}^2} \right), & \text{if } 4 < wind_{speed} < 13 \end{cases}$$

Where S_{nom} is the generator's nominal power, cut_{in} is the turbine's cut in speed, $wind_{nominal}$ is the turbine's nominal speed, and $wind_{speed}$ is the wind's velocity (determined randomly according to the Weibull distribution).

The solar farm injection is given by the product of a random number (generated according to a uniform distribution) and the plant's capacity.

Table 5 – Interruption Cost Depending on the Consumer Type

Consumer Type	Interruption Cost (\$/kWh)
Residential	1.50
Commercial	3.00
Industrial	4.64

Table 6 – Protective/Maneuvering Devices' Cost

Device	Operational Current Range (A)	Acquisition Cost (\$)	Installation/Uninstallation Cost (\$)	Annual Maintenance Cost (\$)	Interrupting Capacity (kA)
Fuse	0-6	300			20
	6-10	400			
	10-15	500			
	15-25	600			
	25-40	700	100	50	80
	40-65	800			
	65-100	900			
	100-140	1000			
	140-200	1100			
Automatic Recloser	0-1000	15000	2000	1000	16
Automatic Sectionalizing Switch	0-1000	3500	800	350	-
Island Interconnection Device	0-1000	20000	2500	1500	16

NSGA-II Parameters

The algorithm developed for this paper adopts the following parameters: population with 500 individuals and 2000 generations. The recombination and mutation indexes are refreshed every generation according to (1) and (2), respectively.

$$T_R^{k+1} = T_R^k - \left(\frac{T_R^0 - T_R^{final}}{N_{ger}} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$T_M^{k+1} = T_M^k - \left(\frac{T_M^0 - T_M^{final}}{N_{ger}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where T_R^k and T_M^k are, respectively, the recombination and mutation indexes at generation k and N_{ger} is the limit of generations. $T_R^0 = 90$, $T_R^{final} = 50$, $T_M^0 = 10$, and $T_M^{final} = 70$.

In addition to the Crowding Distance routine we also employ a Hamming distance calculation as a dissimilarity measure. The potential of each individual within its frontier is given by (3).

$$P_i^k = CD_i^k + HD_i^k \quad (3)$$

Where P_i^k is the potential of an individual i at generation k , CD_i^k is the individual's crowding distance value calculated for generation k , and HD_i^k is the Hamming distance calculated for generation k . Whenever two individuals have similar codification, a negative Hamming distance is attributed to one of them, according to the following parameters:

1. The solution that belongs to the worse frontier receives the negative value;
2. The solution with most constraint violations receives the negative value;
3. The solution with the higher value for the sum of the normalized objective functions receives the negative value.

Individuals with negative potential are replaced with new solutions every generation.

Convergence Analysis

We ran the proposed algorithm 30 times considering the same initial population (generated using a uniform distribution) and the same NSGA-II parameters to evaluate the algorithm's convergence. The non-dominated solutions comprised in each of the 30 non-dominated frontiers were analyzed firstly using the Shapiro-Wilk test to verify normality. However, the null hypothesis could not be accepted in any of the executions. Thus, we applied the Friedman non-parametric test to detect possible differences between the non-dominated frontiers. Also, we applied the Nemenyi *posthoc* test to evaluate the magnitude of difference between the non-dominated frontiers. For most of the scenarios, there is no statistical difference (considering a 95% confidence interval) between the non-dominated frontiers. In 87% of the executions, the algorithm shows convergence for every objective function; in 93% of the executions, the algorithm shows convergence for two objective functions; and, in every case, the algorithm shows convergence for at least one objective function.

Comparison of the cost objective

Comparison of the ENSEC objective

Comparison of the SAIDI objective

Cost

ENSEC

SAIDI

Protection System Design

Table 7 – Protective Devices' Acting Time for Each Fault Situation

Fault Location	Primary PD	Backup PD	Primary PD's Minimum SCC	Backup PD's Maximum SCC	IIDs SCCs (80/107)	Primary PD's Delayed Trip Time	Backup PD's Delayed Trip Time
Branch 52	Fuse at branch 50	Substation Relay	433 A	1564 A (phase) 1091 A (neutral)	108/193 A (phase) 113/190 A (ground)	4,34 s	4,85 s (phase) 4,60 s (neutral)
Branch 84	IID at branch 80	Recloser at Branch 62	429 A (phase) 412 A (ground)	1494 A (phase) 1106 A (neutral)	--/52 A (phase) --/108 A (neutral)	0,09 s (phase) 0,07 s (ground)	0,69 s (phase) 0,27 s (neutral)
Branch 96	Fuse at branch 96	Recloser at Branch 62	368 A	1558 A (phase) 1059 (neutral)	116/208 A (phase) 114/200 A (neutral)	0,03 s	0,68 s (phase) 0,28 s (neutral)

Note: PD – Protective Device; SCC – Short-Circuit Current

Table 8 – Protective Devices Sizing and Parameters

Protective Device	Unit	Curve	Time Dial	Pickup Current	Interrupting Capacity (kA)
Substation Relay	51	Very Inverse	5,5	219 A	16
	51 N	Very Inverse	9,0	35 A	
	50		3,0	265 A	
	50N		3,0	105 A	
Recloser 62	51	Extremely Inverse	5,0	37 A	16
	51 N	Extremely Inverse	2,0	25 A	
	50		2,0	294 A	
	50N		2,0	127 A	
IID 80 (upstream faults)	51	Extremely Inverse	0,5	42 A	16
	51 N	Extremely Inverse	0,5	5 A	
	50		1,0	42 A	
	50N		1,0	5 A	
IID 80 (downstream faults)	51	Extremely Inverse	0,5	19 A	16
	51 N	Extremely Inverse	0,5	11 A	
	50		1,0	376 A	
	50N		1,0	156 A	
IID 107 (upstream faults)	51	Extremely Inverse	0,5	86 A	16
	51 N	Extremely Inverse	0,5	5 A	
	50		1,0	86 A	
	50N		1,0	5 A	
IID 107 (downstream faults)	51	Extremely Inverse	0,5	10 A	16
	51 N	Extremely Inverse	0,5	25 A	
	50		1,0	383 A	
	50N		1,0	157 A	
Fuse at branch 50 (100T)	--	--	--	--	80
Fuse at branch 96 (6T)	--	--	--	--	20
Fuse at branch 4 (6T)	--	--	--	--	20
Fuse at branch 25 (100T)	--	--	--	--	80
Fuse at branch 40 (6T)	--	--	--	--	20
Fuse at branch 41 (100T)	--	--	--	--	80
Fuse at branch 90 (6T)	--	--	--	--	20
Fuse at branch 101 (6T)	--	--	--	--	20